

Detection and removing cosmic ray of space astronomical images based on Artificial Neural Network

Mayada El-Sayed¹, Noha MM. Abdelnabi², I. M. Selim³ & Ibrahim El-henawy¹

1- Dept. of CS Faculty of Computer and Information, Zagazig University

2- Dept. of CS Faculty of Computer and Information Suez University

3- Dept. of CS Faculty of Computer and Artificial Intelligence, University of Sadat City

Abstract:

Artificial neural network modelling has proven effective in impressively wide range of scientific disciplines. To obtain better quality of astronomical images the signatures of transient artifacts such as cosmic rays, satellite trails and scattered cosmic light must be removed. In this paper we have developed an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) method which detection cosmic ray and removing it from the space CCD astronomical images. The method has been trained tested with a conjugate gradient training algorithm using observational data from an astronomical image. This method of detecting and removing cosmic ray from astronomical images is quite general. Our method effectively removes cosmic rays while leaving almost all the image data untouched.

Keywords: Artificial neural network; Cosmic rays; astronomical CCD images

1. Introduction

Cosmic rays are a general term which refers to all the high-energy massive particles, high-energetic speed particle either an atomic nucleus or an electron that are generated outside the solar system. A cosmic ray passing through the visual or infrared detector, can cause generation of a cluster of signal charge [1]. These are energetic charged particles from outer space that travel at nearly the speed of light and accident with the earth at all directions. They are composed mainly of ionized nuclei, roughly 90 % protons, 10 % helium nuclei, and slightly under 1% heavier elements as well as electrons. They are discovered by Victor Hess in 1912, who found that an electroscope discharged faster as ascended in a balloon to altitudes up to 5 km [2]. Victor Hess concluded that cosmic rays arrived from outside our atmosphere and did not originate from decaying radioactive isotopes in the ground. Not only some of these particles originate from the Sun, but also most come from sources outside the solar system. The energy spectrum of cosmic ray sources were natural particle accelerators before particle accelerators were built on earth as well as their elementary composition and abundances.

The space and astronomical digital images response over a large dynamic range of optical wavelength but the performance can be diminished, however, by the presence of cosmic ray in this image [3]. The most common problem of is the cosmic ray when the cosmic ray hits the CCD camera, it causes a bright spot on the image. Cosmic rays are usually easy to recognize because they are much sharper than stars (the high energy particle hits just a couple of pixels). If one is just planning to produce a nice picture, they are very easy to clean out. However, removing them without damaging the real objects (stars or galaxies) can be more tricky, but is possible. The discriminating between cosmic rays and stellar objects in CCD space images is very difficult and importance at the same time for ensuring accurate results, so, the cosmic ray must be detected and removed from the images without any distortion of the digital astronomical space image. The manually process of searching and removing of cosmic ray is an extremely tedious and difficult task [4]. We planned to develop an automated Artificial Neural Network system capable of recognizing, locating, the cosmic ray in images and removing it.

Artificial Neural Network method is used as approximation useful tools for modeling complex, which means they modify themselves as they learn from initial training. These method help to estimate the effective and ideal methods for arriving at solutions and offers solutions for many problems. We propose method for detecting and remove cosmic ray from space CCD images. Artificial Neural Network System can be learn from observing data set of images, as will as well suited to pattern recognition problems. An artificial neural network has been implemented to detecting and removing cosmic ray from astronomical space CCD images by MATLAB. We would like to stress here that our algorithm effectively removes cosmic rays while leaving almost all the image data untouched [3].

2. Proposed Artificial Neural Networks method

An artificial neural network is a group of interconnected computing elements, or neurons, a neuron computes the sum of its inputs (which are either the outputs of other neurons or external inputs to the system) and each neuron has only one output but this output is multiplied by a weighting factor if it is to be used as the input to another neuron and passes this sum through a nonlinear function, such as a hyperbolic tangent or a hard threshold.

The cosmic rays deposit a portion of their signal in the pixels they hit, causing some extra energy in these pixels. The image may have a large range of signal levels in different areas. The neurons are divided into layers, and each neuron is only connected to neurons in adjacent layers, which is

shown schematically in Fig. 1 [5]. The actual neural network architecture makes use of a single hidden layer. The input layer contains 225 neurons, and the output layer has only one neuron, which provides the decision is identified the object whether a stellar object or cosmic ray. Signals from pixels belonging to the training and testing sub frames were presented to input neurons starting from the left corner along the x axis and successively row by row of image. The system is sufficient to solve the problem of discrimination between objects and have little time consuming during learning and operating phases. Furthermore, there are no feedback loops connecting neurons, so the signal produced by an external input move in only one direction (from left to right as Shown in Fig. 1) the output of the system is only the output of the last neuron in the network [6].

Fig 1. Schematic diagram of an artificial neural network system [5].

The neurons of the adjacent layer, and this connection have been characterized by a weight w . Usually the neuron j in the hidden layer derives a weighted sum of all inputs applied to it (the vector \mathbf{x}) and, through a function, produces an output value $y = f(w, \mathbf{x})$ which is passed to the neurons in the next layer, and so on up to the last hidden layer ($i = N - 1$) which produces an output vector. In the cosmic ray detection, the output of the network will be a flag pixel at the point (\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}) in the image. The output of the system is computed using equation 1, [7]:

$$Y^i = f \sum_i w_i x_i \quad (1)$$

Where Y^i is the output of the i^{th} neuron of the $N-1$ level. The output of the i^{th} hidden unit is obtained first by forming a weighted linear combination of the d input values, and then by adding a bias. And d is the number of the input, $W^{(1)}_{j,i}$ denotes a weight in the first layer (from input i to hidden unit j). Note that $w_{j,0}$ denotes the bias for the hidden unit j , and f is a activation. Note that there is only one output neuron in our network. The output of neuron j , would be as in equation 2.

$$out_j(x_j) = \frac{e^{x_j} - 1}{e^{x_j} + 1} = \tanh\left(\frac{x_j}{2}\right) \quad (2)$$

Each neuron in our method computes a hyperbolic tangent function of its inputs. The input to neuron j , x_j , is defined by equation 3 [14].

$$x_j = \sum_i w_{ij} out_i \quad (3)$$

Where w_{ij} is the connection weight from neuron i to neuron j , and out is the output of neuron i (or input i if neuron j is in the first layer). With the error ϵ is defined by equation 4 [9].

$$\epsilon = \frac{1}{2} \sum_p [out_p(w) - target_p]^2 \quad (4)$$

Where the summation is taken over all the training patterns which have been presented to the network in the training set.

3. Dataset and Experimental Result

The data have been used in this work came from actual astronomical observations with the CCD camera system at kottamia 74 inch telescope. Although in principle to train the network we chose to preprocess the data and extract discrete features from it. Because the observation is carried out under different conditions, background levels and average counts are varied from one image to another image. This means that a network can find cosmic ray in one image might not be able to find them in other images [11]. The preprocess is simplify the training system and use the data to calculate various attributes or features of the image at each point (x, y) and use these quantities as the inputs to the network. The coordinates of all the cosmic ray in the image region were found by visual inspection of the image and were then used as inputs to the network. 100 randomly chosen coordinates in that region of images were also supplied to the network as a positions which did not contain cosmic rays. Feature extraction significantly ensure reduces the dimensionality of the input space, which reduces the number of trainings required to achieve good detection performance. Before calculating the feature values to be used by the network, the data were normalized to the average counts in the image according to equation 5:

$$N(X, Y) = \mathbf{1} - \frac{c(X, Y)}{(c)} \quad (5)$$

We analyze relatively small sub frames to work with a more concentrated local distribution of counts. Select small sized sub frames that cover the whole frame, with substantial overlap. The area of sub frame is **A (3x3)** (this area of thee pixel in row and three pixel in column is equal 9

square pixels). The signal coming from cosmic rays does not have a Gaussian distribution. The label on the current pixel is (X, Y) , where X is the column number and Y is the row number. This should reflect in the distribution of counts in the sub frame of image affected by cosmic rays. The features described here are calculated for each sub frames of pixels in the image. The normalized intensity at each point of $N(X, Y)$ is $I = N(X, Y)$.and the features are labeled from F_1 to F_3 . Each feature is labeled to indicate which network is used in.

Feature 1: Intensity in central sub frame $F_1 = N(X, Y)$.

Feature 2: Intensity variance in maximum nearest pixels is computed using equation 6 [9].

$$F_2 = \left(\frac{1}{25} \sum_{i=-2}^2 \sum_{j=-2}^2 N^2(X+i, Y+j) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (6)$$

Feature 3: Number of pixels with intensities clustered around central pixel intensity is computed using equation 7 [9].

$$F_3 = \sum_{i=-2}^2 \sum_{j=-2}^2 \max [N(X+i, Y+j) - D^*, 0] \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Where } D^* = \left\{ 1 - [1 - D(c, r)]^{\frac{2}{3}} \right\}$$

For the detection the cosmic ray in our system, network given three input features, 5 neurons in the first layer, 6 neurons in the second layer, and one output neuron. The output of the network ranged between -1 and 1, with all outputs greater than the specific value with minimum error interpreted to mean that a cosmic ray was presented at the current point in the image [6][11]. Adjusting the weights is equivalent to moving the boundaries of the decision regions around until appropriate decisions are made by the network. The sequence steps is as the follows:

- 1) Set the weights to random values between - 1 and 1.
- 2) Present network with several input vectors ("training patterns") and network responses.
- 3) Calculate the output of the network for each of these training vectors.
- 4) Calculate the sum of errors between the outputs and the responses of the network.
- 5) Depending on whether the sub frame is a part of a cosmic ray or not, the error ϵ is defined by equation 8 [9],

$$\epsilon = \frac{1}{2} \sum_p [out_p(w) - target_p]^2 \quad (8)$$

Where the summation is taken over all the training patterns which have been presented to the network in the training set. This procedure defines a positive error value ϵ for each possible combination of weight values. To find the minimum of ϵ in weight space training method terminates when the network error is less than a previously determined convergence criterion. In our implementation we decided to substitute the cosmic rays with the average of the counts in the neighboring pixels.

Conclusion

Recently, many digital sky surveys in a wide range of wavelengths are producing huge databases of astronomical image. Automated tool for analyzing astronomical data images and objects, such as galaxies, star, cluster, and nose, is very important tools, because rapidly collected data by modern projects is a need to create a good solution [12]. This main that we required only three features to detect and removing cosmic ray from the astronomical space images. The cosmic ray detection lists based on neural network is about 95% of all the cosmic rays. In a sense, the average difference in feature space between any cosmic ray and the background is larger than the difference between the cosmic ray and bright staller object. This is true for any computational or automated technique because neural networks (artificial intelligence) are thought as people often feel that they do not need to set up the problem. We caution the reader that proper problem definition and setup are important for pattern recognition with neural networks, just as they are for any computational technique. However, it is important to be sure that the detection problem is well-posed and that the training set is as complete as possible. The automated ANN detecting system can be quite effective for small exposure times. It begins by extracting relevant features from the data, and small probability of long cosmic ray signatures. It may be possible to check only images with exposure time of at least a few seconds and to find those images [13]. Recently, automated techniques coupled with computational developed astronomical system leading to better understanding of different stellar objects and their development process also leads to better understanding of the past, present, and future of our planet, solar system, galaxy and the universe [14]. We found that the performance of the system of detection and removing all cosmic ray from the astronomical images based on neural networks was optimized when we used.

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